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BRAIN GATE

Ms.D.Indhumathi , Ms.V.Rudhra devi , Ms.A.Ramya

II M.Sc Software Systems

Sri krishna arts and science college, coimbatore,India

Abstract

Brain gate is an electrode chip it can be used to implement in the brain.the electrical signal exchanged by neurons within the brain after implementing it into the brain. That signals are sent to the brain and it executes body movement. Special software is used to handle the signalling process.The computer is controlled by the patient once the signal is sent to the computer. If man forgot about his past due to certain accidental matter or he had lost his part of his body, at that time the electrode chip will be implanted on his brain and active the man .The goal of the Brain Gate program is to develop a fast and reliable connection between the brain of a severely disabled person and a personal computer. The 'Brain Gate' device can provide paralysed or motor-impaired patients a mode of communication through the translation of thought into direct computer control.

Keywords: Computer Brain interface, Motor cortex

INTRODUCTION

The system consists of a sensor that is implanted on the motor cortex of the brain (Pedestal) and a Brain Gate Neural Interface Device that analyzes the signal. The intact brain functions, brain signals are generated even though they are not sent to the arms, hands and legs,this is the principle.^[2] The signals are interpreted and translated into cursor movements, offering the user an alternate "BRAIN GATE PATHWAY" to control a computer with thought, just as man who have the ability to move their hands.

Figure 1: Brain gate

WORKING

The Brain Gate neural interface device is a propriety brain-computer interface the consist of an Inter neural signal sensor and External Processor.^[3] The sensor consists of a tiny chip. That tiny chip contains 100 microscopic electrodes. 100 microscopic electrodes used to detect brain cell electrical activity. In motor cortex area of brain the chip is implanted that controls movement. Covert neural signals into an output signal by external processor under the users own control. In the pilot version of the device, computers contains cart, that connects a cable sensor to an external processor. Using custom decoding software, create the communication output and the computer translates brain activity.

Figure 2: working of brain gate

Brain Computer Interface Technology (BCI)

“BCIs” usually connects the brain (or nervous system) with a computer system. A Brain computer Interface, called as direct neural interface or brain machine interface is a direct communication pathway between human or animal brain and an external device.

Figure 3: BCI

TYPES OF BRAIN COMPUTER INTERFACE

1. One way BCI

Computer either accepts command from brain or send signal to it (for example, restore vision) but not both.^[2]

2. Two way BCI

Brain and external devices can exchange information in both direction but have yet to be implanted animals or humans.

Components

Based on features

Invasive

Partially invasive BCI

Noninvasive BCI

How the brain control motor function?

The brain is “hardwired” with this connections, that are made by billions of neurons that can make electricity whenever they stimulated. Brain waves, the called electrical patterns.^[1] Neurons acts like the wires and gates in a computer, transmitting, gathering and electrochemical signals over distances as far as several feet. The brain cannot encodes information by relying on single neurons, it can be encode by spreading it across large populations of neurons, and by fatsly adapting to new circumstances.

COMPONENTS USED FOR BCI

Neuro chip: A 4-millimeter square silicon chip studded with 100 hair-thin microelectrodes is embedded in the primary motor cortex the region of the brain responsible for controlling movement.

Connector: When the user thinks “move cursor down and up”, in a distinctive pattern the cortical neurons fire; the signal is transmitted through the pedestal plug attached to the skull.

Converter: The signal travels to a shoebox-sized amplifier mounted on the user’s wheelchair, there it is converted into optical data and bounced by fiber-optic cable to a computer.

Computer: It translates brain activity and creates the communication output using custom decoding software.

Challenges Faced By Brain Gate:

It is very luxurious.

The latest technology is 20 bits/min, which is in information transfer rate.

Adaptation and learning is difficult

ADVANTAGES

- Controlling remote device
- Making and receiving telephone calls
- Accessing the internet.
- Turn on or off the lights
- Control robotic arm
- Watch and control television
- Motorized wheel chair

Figure 4: Advantages and Disadvantages of Brain gate

DISADVANTAGES

- Expensive
- Risky Surgery
- Not Wireless yet

- Adaptation and learning difficult.

APPLICATIONS

- In classification of EEG signal.
 - In hypermedia communiqué.
 - Activated control of mobile robot by human EEG.
 - As a brain controlled switch for asynchronous control.^[1]
 - In evaluating the machine learning procedures.
 - The Brain Gate Neural Interface System is a new medical device that is being developed to improve the quality of life for physically disabled people by allowing them to quickly and reliably control a wide range of devices.
 - The Brain Gate System will allow these with severe motor disabilities
- to use their own arms and hands again.
- It may be able to provide an individual with the ability to control devices that allows to breathe, bladder and bowel movements.^[1]
 - The Brain Gate System is designed to restore functionality for severely motor-impaired individuals.

CONCLUSION

Two patients have been implanted with the Brain Gate system.^[1]

- Using the system, called Brain Gate, the patient can read e-mail, and he can play games in system, he can on or off the lights and he can able to change channels or adjust the volume of a television set.

Figure 5: Brain gate

- In early test sessions, the patient was able to control the TV and carry on a conversation and move his head at the same time.
- The results are spectacular and almost unbelievable.^[3]

□ Brain Gate can help paralyzed people move by controlling their own electric wheel chairs, communicate by using e-mail and Internet-based telephone systems, and be independent by controlling things such as televisions and thermostats.

□ At last BRAIN GATE has been proved to be boon for paralyzed patient.^[1]

CURRENT WORK PROGRESS

Brain Gate is currently recruiting patients with a range of neuromuscular and neuron-degenerative conditions for pilot clinical trials being conducted under an Investigational Device Exemption (IDE). Cyber kinetics, it hopes to refine the Brain Gate in the next two years to develop a wireless device, that will not have a plug, it is less visible and makes safer.^[2] There is potential for a wide variety of further applications once the basics of brain mapping are worked out.

REFERENCE

□ [1] *Journal of Research in Technology & Management*.

□ [2] "A direct brain interface based on event-related potentials". *h*

□ [3] [http:// www.wikipedia.org](http://www.wikipedia.org)